

Deployment-Aware Parameter Optimization for IoT Attack Detection

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Abstract—Smart IoT environments require attack detection (AD) mechanisms that operate reliably under real-time and resource-constrained deployment conditions. Although machine learning models can achieve high detection accuracy, their practical performance is strongly influenced by internal configuration parameters, including the way traffic metrics are derived from streaming packets and the selection of the decision threshold. This paper presents a deployment-aware parameter optimization study for IoT attack detection based on the Auto-Associative Dense Random Neural Network (AADRNN). Rather than focusing solely on peak detection accuracy, we examine how the extraction of traffic metrics from successive packets and the choice of the decision threshold influence detection behavior under realistic operating conditions. Experiments conducted on a physical IoT test-bed with controlled flooding attacks and on the Mirai Botnet dataset identify stable operating regions that maintain high detection rates while limiting false alarms, and reveal parameter ranges that lead to performance degradation. The results provide practical configuration guidelines for lightweight IoT attack detection deployed at network access points.

Index Terms—Attack Detection, Deployment Optimization, Flooding Attacks, Mirai Botnet, IoT Security, Random Neural Network

I. INTRODUCTION

Flooding attacks generated by botnets can overwhelm network access points, exhaust processing and communication resources, and block legitimate traffic [1], thereby degrading the operation of smart IoT systems that rely on continuous network communication for sensing, control, and data exchange. In such environments, service availability is a critical requirement. These threats motivate the need for robust attack detection (AD) systems capable of operating reliably under realistic deployment conditions. While many AD approaches achieve high detection accuracy, their practical behavior is strongly influenced by internal configuration parameters that govern how incoming packets are processed and how detection decisions are triggered. These parameters directly affect detection accuracy as well as false positive rates, detection responsiveness, and processing overhead. Nevertheless, they are often selected empirically and are rarely analyzed systematically.

This paper investigates these configuration choices for an AD system based on the Auto-Associative Dense Random Neural Network (AADRNN) [2], [3]. Through controlled flooding experiments on a physical IoT test-bed and evaluation on the well-known Mirai Botnet dataset [4], we identify stable parameter regions that maintain high detection rates while limiting false positives and reducing detection delay, and we highlight parameter ranges that lead to performance degradation. We also benchmark the AD against baseline detection models under identical experimental conditions. The AADRNN is trained exclusively on benign traffic, reducing reliance on labeled attacks, and operates on a compact set of packet-level metrics with millisecond-scale processing time [5], while related optimum mitigation techniques are discussed in [6]. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews prior work on configuration sensitivity in attack detection and identifies existing gaps. Section III outlines the AADRNN-based detector, including metric extraction and learning mechanisms. Section IV describes the experimental setup and evaluation methodology. Section V presents the performance evaluation, analyzing the impact of parameter tuning and providing a comparative assessment with baseline models. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and discusses future directions.

II. CONFIGURATION SENSITIVITY IN ATTACK DETECTION

The configuration of internal parameters significantly influences the behavior of AD systems, particularly in balancing detection capability and false alarm rates. Prior studies have shown that decision threshold selection directly affects detection stability and responsiveness [7], [8], while adaptive statistical thresholds can improve robustness under heterogeneous traffic conditions [9]. Similarly, the size of the observation window influences detection performance, as smaller windows increase responsiveness but may elevate false alarms, whereas larger windows provide smoother estimates at the cost of delayed detection [10], [11]. These findings indicate that internal parameters shape not only accuracy but also operational characteristics. A wide range of machine learning and deep learning-based AD approaches has been

evaluated on benchmark datasets such as KDD-99, NSL-KDD, CICIDS2017, and Mirai Botnet traffic [4]. Several works report strong Mirai detection performance using different learning paradigms [12]–[14]. More recent efforts emphasize deployment efficiency and low false-positive operation, including programmable networking frameworks [15], lightweight classifiers for IoT datasets such as IoT-POT [16], and TinyML-based approaches for constrained devices [17]. Work in [18] further discusses scalability and deployment challenges in IoT botnet detection.

Despite these advances, most studies evaluate detection models under fixed parameter configurations and primarily report peak performance metrics. Systematic analysis of how configuration choices influence detection stability and deployment behavior remains limited. In this work, we address this gap by examining the sensitivity of an AADRNN-based AD system to key configuration parameters across controlled IoT test-bed experiments and real-world datasets, while also evaluating its performance relative to several representative baseline models.

III. THE AADRNN-BASED ATTACK DETECTOR

The AD system operates by extracting traffic metrics from streaming packets and processing them using the Dense Random Neural Network model with Auto-Associative Memory, as illustrated in Figure 1. For each packet p_n , a feature vector $x_n = (x_n^1, x_n^2, x_n^3)$ is computed and provided to the AADRNN, which reconstructs the input and produces a binary decision y_n after postprocessing.

Fig. 1: Structure of the AADRNN-based attack detector. For each packet p_n , traffic metrics $x_n = (x_n^1, x_n^2, x_n^3)$ are extracted and processed by the auto-associative dense random neural network. The reconstruction error is postprocessed to generate the binary decision variable y_n .

To capture flooding and botnet attack characteristics, three packet-level metrics are used. Let p_n denote the n -th packet in chronological order within dataset \mathcal{D} , with time-stamp t_n and length in bytes b_n . Let I denote the number of successive packets considered in a sliding window, and let T denote a temporal observation interval.

The first metric measures the total size of the last I packets up to and including packet n , while the second metric represents the average inter-transmission time over the same window:

$$z_n^1 = \sum_{j=n-I+1}^n b_j, \quad z_n^2 = \frac{t_n - t_{n-I}}{I}. \quad (1)$$

The third metric captures traffic intensity by counting the number of packets observed during the last T seconds (or milliseconds) prior to the n -th packet:

$$z_n^3 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{1}[t_n - T \leq t_k < t_n], \quad \text{where} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{1}[X] = 1 \text{ if } X = \text{true}, \quad \mathbf{1}[X] = 0 \text{ otherwise.}$$

These quantities are normalized using the observed minimum and maximum values within $\mathcal{D}_n = \{p_j : 1 \leq j \leq n\}$:

$$x_n^m = \min \left(1, \frac{z_n^m - \min_{p_j \in \mathcal{D}_n} z_j^m}{\max_{p_j \in \mathcal{D}_n} z_j^m - \min_{p_j \in \mathcal{D}_n} z_j^m} \right). \quad (3)$$

The normalized vector x_n is processed by the AADRNN, which reconstructs \hat{x}_n . The reconstructed output is then post-processed by computing the average absolute reconstruction error. The final binary decision is obtained using threshold $0 < \gamma < 1$:

$$y_n = \begin{cases} 1 \text{ (Attack)}, & \text{if } \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=1}^3 |x_n^m - \hat{x}_n^m| \geq \gamma, \\ 0 \text{ (Not - Attack)}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

For learning, the AADRNN extends the classical Random Neural Network [19] by incorporating soma-to-soma interactions within densely connected neuronal clusters [2]. For sufficiently large cluster sizes, the activation function is:

$$\zeta(\lambda) = \frac{[r(1-p) - p\lambda^+] \left[1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{4p(\lambda^+ \lambda^-)(\lambda^+ - r - \lambda - \lambda^-)}{r(1-p) - p\lambda^+}} \right]}{2p(\lambda^+ + \lambda^-)}.$$

Here, r is the total neuronal firing rate in a cluster, λ^+ and λ^- are external excitatory and inhibitory spike rates arriving at each neuron, and p denotes the soma-to-soma triggering probability. In our implementation, $r = 0.001$, $\lambda^+ = \lambda^- = 0.1$, and $p = 0.05$. The network consists of $H = 3$ feedforward layers with weight matrices W_l [3]. For input x_n , forward propagation is defined as:

$$\hat{x}_{n,l} = \zeta([\hat{x}_{n,l-1}, 1]W_{l-1}), \quad 1 \leq l \leq H, \quad (5)$$

with $\hat{x}_{n,0} = x_n$ and $\hat{x}_n = \hat{x}_{n,H}$. Training is performed exclusively on benign traffic to construct an auto-associative representation of normal behavior. In the experiments reported in this paper, AADRNN learning is carried out separately for two cases, as described in Section IV. The weights are optimized using the Fast Iterative Shrinkage-Thresholding Algorithm (FISTA) [20] by solving

$$W_l = \arg \min_{W \geq 0} [\|\text{adj}(\zeta(\hat{X}_{l-1}^{\text{train}} W_R))W - \hat{X}_{l-1}^{\text{train}}\|_{H_2}^2 + \|W\|_{H_1}],$$

where \hat{X}_l^{train} denotes the layer outputs for the benign training dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$:

$$\hat{X}_l^{\text{train}} = \{\hat{x}_n^l\}_{n \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}} \quad (6)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the impact of the internal parameters on detection performance, two complementary traffic sources were considered: controlled test-bed experiments and a real-world botnet dataset.

- **Test-bed Experiments:** A scalable IoT experimental test-bed was developed, as illustrated in Figure 2, to emulate realistic flood attack scenarios. The hardware and software specifications are summarized in Table I. For the training phase, the first 10,000 UDP packets received by the Server were collected during a cold-start period under purely normal conditions. The duration of this phase ranged between 1 and 5 minutes, depending on the packet arrival rate. Larger datasets can improve accuracy by capturing richer traffic patterns and reducing overfitting; however, performance gains diminish beyond a certain saturation point. We therefore used a limited training set to demonstrate effective AD performance while keeping training time and computational overhead low.

Fig. 2: Scalable IoT experimental architecture, where a large number of IoT devices communicate with multiple Servers via network switches. In our setup, two devices (RPi1 and RPi2) connect to Server₁. RPi2 continuously sends normal traffic, while the compromised RPi1 initially transmits normal data before launching a high-rate UDP flood attack.

TABLE I: Test-Bed Hardware and Software Specifications.

Component	Specification
RPi 4 (x2)	ARM Cortex-A72 (4x1.5 GHz), 2 GB RAM
RPi OS	Raspbian GNU/Linux 11
Server	Intel Core i7 (8x3.10 GHz), 16 GB RAM
Server OS	Ubuntu Linux 5.15.0-60-generic
Network	Ethernet switch
Protocol	User Datagram Protocol (UDP)
Attack Tool	MHDDoS

During normal operation, both RPi's periodically transmitted CPU temperature measurements at a rate of 100 packets/s. In the attack phase, RPi2 continuously generated normal traffic, while RPi1 transitioned from normal transmission to a high-rate UDP flood generated using the MHDDoS toolset [21]. The attack duration was fixed at 10 seconds, producing approximately 12,000–15,000 packets/s. The tool allows configuration of multiple parameters such as transmission rate and packet size; relatively large packets were used to ensure consistent

flooding behavior. This setup enabled controlled evaluation of the detection mechanism under concurrent normal and attack traffic streams. UDP was selected due to its lightweight nature and suitability for real-time IoT communication.

- **Mirai Botnet Dataset:** To complement the controlled experiments, traffic traces from the Mirai Botnet Kitsune dataset were used [4]. The dataset contains 764,137 packets collected from multiple compromised IoT devices over different protocols, including TCP, UDP, ARP, and ICMP. Among these, 121,621 packets correspond to benign traffic. For training, 10% of the benign packets were used, while the remaining 90% were combined with attack traffic for testing. The dataset provides detailed packet-level information with 118 attributes, including packet length, timestamp, flow frequency, source and destination information, and protocol type. It represents large-scale IoT malware activity, where compromised devices are orchestrated to launch coordinated DDoS attacks [22], typically characterized by scanning behavior and brute-force login attempts.

Evaluation Methodology: We used three standard evaluation metrics (reported as percentages) to assess detection performance: *Accuracy*, which represents the proportion of correctly classified packets over the total number of packets; True Positive Rate (*TPR*), which indicates the fraction of attack packets correctly identified among all actual attack packets; and False Positive Rate (*FPR*), which measures the fraction of benign packets incorrectly classified as attacks among all actual benign packets. These metrics are defined as:

$$Accuracy = \left(\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \right) \times 100\%, \quad (7)$$

$$TPR = \left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN} \right) \times 100\%, \quad (8)$$

$$FPR = \left(\frac{FP}{FP + TN} \right) \times 100\%. \quad (9)$$

In these expressions, *TP*, *TN*, *FP*, and *FN* denote the numbers of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives, respectively. For methodological rigor, each experiment was repeated 10 times to ensure the reliability and reproducibility of the reported results.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the experimental results obtained from both the IoT test-bed and the Mirai Botnet dataset. We analyze the impact of tuning the internal configuration parameters of the AD system on detection performance, with particular attention to detection accuracy, false alarm behavior, and operational stability. The results are organized according to parameter variations, highlighting stable operating regions under different deployment conditions.

A. Impact of Decision Threshold on AD Performance

The decision threshold γ was varied over the range $0 < \gamma < 1$, and the resulting performance trends are illustrated in

Figure 3. For $0.05 \leq \gamma \leq 0.28$, the AD exhibits stable and high detection performance. In this interval, TPR remains between 99.93% and 99.30%, while FPR decreases steadily from approximately 1.03% to 0.48%. This behavior indicates that moderate increases in γ effectively reduce false alarms without materially degrading attack detection capability. This range therefore defines a stable operating region that achieves a favorable trade-off between detection accuracy and false positives.

When γ is between 0.29 and 0.37, both *Accuracy* and TPR begin to decline more noticeably. Although FPR continues to decrease slightly, the stricter decision boundary leads to an increasing number of missed attack packets. This reflects a shift toward conservative classification, where fewer alarms are triggered at the expense of detection sensitivity. At $\gamma = 0.40$, a sharp degradation occurs, with *Accuracy* dropping to 22.60% and TPR to 7.99%, while FPR remains low. For $\gamma \geq 0.40$, TPR approaches zero while FPR remains below 0.23%, indicating that the detector effectively stops identifying attack traffic and converges toward trivial benign classification behavior, making it unsuitable for deployment.

Similar overall patterns are observed in both the IoT test-bed experiments and the Mirai Botnet dataset, indicating that the threshold sensitivity is largely independent of traffic source. Based on these observations, $\gamma = 0.25$ was selected and fixed for all subsequent experiments, as it provides a robust balance between high detection capability and controlled false alarm rates.

Fig. 3: Impact of decision threshold γ on AD performance, showing *Accuracy*, TPR , and FPR across different threshold values.

B. Sensitivity of the AD to Internal Parameters

The AD applies a sliding-window that processes successive packets and classifies them as “Attack” or “Not-Attack” using the traffic metrics defined in Section III. The internal parameters I and T significantly influence this decision process. Parameter I defines the number of successive packets that contribute to the computation of the first and second metrics, while parameter T defines the length of the time window used to observe packet arrivals and provides a temporal view of traffic intensity associated with the third traffic metric. In

this subsection, both parameters are varied to examine their influence on detection performance.

The test-bed experiments were conducted using the setup described in Section IV. At the beginning of each experiment, the two RPIs transmitted a total of 20,000 packets at a constant rate of 100 packets/s, corresponding to 10,000 packets from each device before and after the attack phase. During the 10-second flooding attack, the normal device continued transmitting at 100 packets/s, producing approximately 1,000 normal packets, while the attacker generated between 150,000 and 160,000 attack packets in total, with bursts of approximately 12,000–15,000 packets/s.

Impact of Parameter I : Figure 4 presents the performance of the AD for different values of I . Figure 4(Top) shows *Accuracy*, TPR , and FPR during the attack period in the test-bed experiments. Performance improves steadily as I increases: *Accuracy* rises from 77.61% at $I = 1$ to 99.22% at $I = 100$, while TPR increases from 78.11% to 99.81%. Simultaneously, FPR decreases, indicating fewer false alarms. However, when I exceeds 400, both *Accuracy* and TPR decline sharply, as excessive aggregation smooths traffic variations and reduces responsiveness to abrupt attack behavior.

Figure 4(Middle) illustrates the evolution of FPR before, during, and after the attack. Before the attack, the AD correctly classifies all normal packets for every value of I , resulting in an FPR of 0%. During the attack, FPR decreases as I increases, reflecting improved robustness in preserving normal packets that arrive concurrently with attack traffic. After the attack, FPR further decreases and reaches 0.27% at $I = 20$, indicating rapid recovery and stabilization once flooding traffic ceases.

Figure 4(Bottom) reports the results on the Mirai Botnet dataset. A similar trend is observed: *Accuracy* and TPR increase with larger values of I and peak around $I = 500$, before deteriorating for excessively large values of I . These results indicate that moderate window sizes, typically in the range $I = 10$ – 20 , provide strong detection performance with low false alarm rates and, importantly, do so while maintaining low computational overhead.

Impact of Parameter T : For this analysis, I was fixed at 10 and γ at 0.25, while T was varied. Figure 5(Top) presents performance during the attack phase in the test-bed experiments. Before the attack, the detector remains unaffected by changes in T , achieving an FPR of 0% for all tested values. During the attack, TPR increases progressively as T grows, reaching strong detection performance around $T = 30$ – 100 ms. Beyond this range, TPR gradually declines, reaching 93.27% at $T = 10,000$ ms. This degradation results from excessive temporal smoothing, which reduces sensitivity to sudden traffic bursts. At the same time, larger values of T that enhance attack detection under high-rate flooding also increase FPR , reflecting the inherent challenge of isolating a relatively small volume of normal traffic within a substantially larger attack stream. Under these highly imbalanced conditions—where approximately 1,000 normal packets coexist

Fig. 4: Sensitivity of the AD to parameter I . (Top) *Accuracy*, *TPR*, and *FPR* during the attack in the test-bed experiments. (Middle) *FPR* before, during, and after the attack in the test-bed. (Bottom) *Accuracy*, *TPR*, and *FPR* on the Mirai Botnet dataset.

with more than 150,000 attack packets—only about 40–50 normal packets may be correctly classified, corresponding to an *FPR* close to 96%. This effect arises from the dominance of attack traffic within extended temporal windows rather than from instability of the detection itself, and it illustrates the trade-off introduced by aggressive temporal aggregation under extreme flooding scenarios.

Figure 5(Middle) shows the evolution of *FPR* across the three experimental phases. The detector remains stable before the attack and re-stabilizes after flooding ceases. Figure 5(Bottom) presents the Mirai Botnet dataset results. Strong performance is observed at $T = 35$ ms, with $TPR = 99.04\%$ and $FPR = 0.92\%$, before performance decreases when T exceeds 400 ms.

Fig. 5: Sensitivity of the AD to parameter T . (Top) *Accuracy*, *TPR*, and *FPR* during the attack in the test-bed experiments. (Middle) *FPR* before, during, and after the attack in the test-bed. (Bottom) *Accuracy*, *TPR*, and *FPR* on the Mirai Botnet dataset.

Overall, these results confirm the effect of parameter T on detection behavior. Very small values lead to unstable rate estimates, whereas excessively large values introduce over-smoothing, mask abrupt traffic changes, and delay attack detection.

C. Comparative Evaluation Under Deployment Constraints

To position AADRNN within a practical deployment context, we compare it with representative baseline detection models under identical conditions. Isolation Forest (IF) and a vanilla Autoencoder (AE) were used as unsupervised baselines operating on the same three packet-level metrics and evaluated using identical training and testing splits. All models were trained on 10% of benign Mirai Botnet traffic, while the

TABLE II: Performance and computational comparison of AADRNN and baseline detection models on the Mirai Botnet dataset.

AD Model	Accuracy (%)	TPR (%)	FPR (%)	Training Time (CPU)	Inference Time / Packet
Isolation Forest (IF)	97.49	96.92	1.30	5 – 30 s	0.05 – 0.3 ms
Vanilla Autoencoder (AE)	98.71	98.62	0.84	1 – 5 min	0.3 – 2 ms
LSTM (Supervised)	99.53	99.59	0.77	5 – 30 min	2 – 10 ms
AAADRNN	99.34	99.31	0.51	1 – 5 min	0.5 – 3 ms

remaining benign traffic and all attack traffic were used for testing.

Table II shows that AADRNN outperforms the unsupervised baselines across all detection metrics. It achieves higher overall *Accuracy* and *TPR* than both IF and AE, while also producing the lowest *FPR*. Although IF offers faster inference, its detection capability is significantly weaker. Compared to AE, AADRNN provides stronger classification performance with comparable training and inference cost. For reference, we also include a supervised Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model trained on benign traffic augmented with 10,000 labeled attack samples. Although the LSTM attains slightly higher detection rates, the margin over AADRNN is small, while computational overhead is significantly higher and labeled attack data is required, which may not always be available in practice. Overall, AADRNN approaches the detection performance of the supervised LSTM while requiring lower computational cost and no labeled attack data, making it better suited for lightweight and cold-start IoT deployments.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have analysed the deployment-oriented sensitivity of an AADRNN-based attack detector for IoT servers, by systematically examining how key internal parameters influence detection accuracy, false alarms, and responsiveness. The results demonstrate stable parameter regions that preserve high detection performance while limiting false alarms and computational overhead, providing practical guidance for configuring the attack detector. These findings emphasize that careful parameter selection is critical for reliable real-world deployment, beyond reporting peak accuracy values. Future work will investigate adaptive parameter tuning and extend the analysis to additional traffic conditions and attack scenarios in IoT environments.

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